

DEPRESSION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS: LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Aim of the Study: This thesis aims to comprehensively explore the prevalence, causes, clinical manifestations, diagnosis, and interventions related to depression among medical students. By synthesizing recent literature, the study endeavors to contribute to a deeper understanding of depression within the medical student community.

Keywords: Depression, Medical Students, Mental Health, Academic Stress, Coping Mechanisms, Burnout, Support Programs, Well-being, Professional Development

Materials and Methods: A thorough search was conducted across various databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, PsycINFO, Embase, and institutional libraries, focusing on depression among medical students. Only articles published within the last decade were included. The synthesis of data aimed to illuminate prevalence rates, contributing factors, clinical presentations, diagnostic strategies, and intervention options for depression in this population.

Outcomes: The study highlights the significance of timely identification and management of depression among medical students for academic success and overall well-being. It emphasizes the varied long-term impacts of depression, including academic underperformance, burnout, and compromised mental health, underscoring the need for effective interventions tailored to individual needs.

Clinical Manifestations and Implications: Depression among medical students manifests across academic, social, and personal domains, impacting various aspects of their lives such as increased stress, sleep disturbances, and compromised mental health. Early intervention strategies, including counseling and mental health support, are crucial for mitigating adverse outcomes associated with depression.

Diagnostic Approaches: Diagnosing depression among medical students requires a nuanced approach, integrating self-report measures, clinical interviews, and psychological assessments. Recognizing unique stressors within medical education is vital for accurate diagnosis, facilitating tailored interventions aligned with students' challenges.

Interventions and Strategies: Treatment modalities for depression among medical students include psychoeducation, counseling, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and pharmacotherapy where indicated. Proactive strategies such as stress management workshops and mindfulness practices contribute to a supportive

learning environment. Individualized interventions considering severity of symptoms and additional mental health concerns are essential.

Conclusion: This abstract underscores the multifaceted nature of depression among medical students and its impact on academic and personal life. By addressing its causes, manifestations, diagnosis, and interventions, the study advocates for a comprehensive approach to support the well-being of medical students within the educational setting.

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